

ANALYSIS OF SANDWICH BEAM WITH STRUCTURALLY GRADED CORE FOR CONCENTRATED LOAD

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SUMMARY: Introduction of concentrated loads into sandwich structures continues to be a difficult challenge in sandwich design, because of the thin face sheets and the low stiffness of the core. The introduction of stiff and strong core inserts improves the structural performance of the sandwich structure, but it also introduces new weak spots in the structure at the junction between the stiff core insert and the more compliant main core. Here, it is proposed to use structurally graded intermediate core between the core insert and the main core material. The structurally graded core material is designed such that it fits the elastic properties of its neighbouring core. The analysis shows that this design is beneficial, provided that the length of the structurally graded core is of sufficient magnitude.

KEYWORDS: Load introduction, sandwich structures, graded materials, cellular foams.

INTRODUCTION

Sandwich structures are typically made as three layered assemblies comprising two thin, stiff and strong face sheets separated by a thick, compliant and lightweight core material. This construction has gained widespread acceptance as an excellent way to obtain extremely lightweight components and structures with very high bending stiffness, high strength and high buckling resistance, see e.g. Zenkert [1] or Allen [2]. Sandwich structures are often used in light weight applications such as aircraft, marine applications and wind turbine blades.

Introducing concentrated loads into a sandwich structure should be done with much care in order to avoid core indentation and local bending of the face sheets, which leads to reduced strength of the sandwich structure. The preferred design solution is to introduce stiff core inserts made from wood, metal or dense polymeric foams under the concentrated load, see fig. 1 (left).

This design introduces new difficulties near the junction between the core insert and the main core where stress concentrations in the core and local bending of the faces sheets will occur due to the different elastic properties of the two core materials. This was analysed analytically by Skvortsov and Thomsen [3], who found that the ratio of shear moduli was the governing parameter. The model of Skvortsov and Thomsen was investigated experimentally by Bozhevolnaya et al. [4], who confirmed the existence of localised bending of the face sheets near the core junction, and applied the analysis to sandwich panels with axi-symmetric inserts, see Bozhevolnaya et. al. [5].

Fig. 1: Sandwich assembly with a stiff core insert for the support of a concentrated load (left). Sandwich assembly with a stiff core insert, which is connected to the main core via a structurally graded material (right).

To attenuate the stress concentrations near the core junctions, it is suggested here that a structurally graded core material is inserted between the main core material and the core insert, see fig. 1 (right). The structurally graded core should be designed such that the elastic properties near the main core should fit the elastic properties of the main core. Then the elastic properties should increase length wise such that the highest elastic properties are located near the core insert.

The investigation will be carried out using a high order sandwich beam theory which has been developed by Frostig et al. [6]. A number of design parameters will be considered, such as the length of the structurally graded core, and the lengthwise shape/variation of the elastic properties.

ANALYSIS

High order sandwich beam theory

The analysis of the sandwich beams, which is applied here, is based on a high order sandwich beam theory, which was suggested by Frostig et al. [6]. The theory is constructed using a layered approach, where the faces are treated as Bernoulli-Euler beams, and are assumed to be perfectly bonded to the core materials at the face-core interfaces. The core is assumed to be a linear elastic continuum, which has negligible stiffness in the in-plane direction. The accuracy of this theory has been investigated by Swanson and Kim [7] for the three point bending load case.

From theory of elasticity, these assumptions lead to a closed-form solution of the core stress field. This closed-form solution predicts that the core shear stresses (τ_{xz}) are constant through the thickness, and that the transverse normal stresses (σ_{zz}) vary linearly through the core thickness.

Governing equations

The governing equations are posed as a system of 14 first order linear differential equations:

$$\frac{d}{dx} \underline{y} = \underline{A} \cdot \underline{y}$$

The governing equations are described using the following state variables:

- y is the vector of fundamental variables;
 $y = \{u_1, u_2, w_1, w_2, \beta_1, \beta_2, N_1, N_2, M_1, M_2, Q_1, Q_2, \tau_{xz}, \tau_{xz,x}/E_c(x)\}$

- u_1, u_2 : the in-plane displacements of the faces
- w_1, w_2 : the transverse displacements
- β_1, β_2 : the rotations of the face sheets
- N_1, N_2 : the in-plane normal stress resultants
- M_1, M_2 : the bending moment resultants
- Q_1, Q_2 the transverse shear resultant in the faces
- τ_{xz} the shear stress in the core.
- $\tau_{xz,x}/E_c(x)$ the gradient of the shear stress in the core normalised with respect to the Young's modulus of the core.

The governing equations were solved numerically using a finite difference scheme based on the Lobatto stage III formula; see e.g. Ascher et al. [8].

The fundamental variables are arranged such that they can be integrated directly, while the continuity across core junctions is satisfied for the displacements and stress resultants governing the core in addition to the shear stress and the displacements in the core layer.

NUMERICAL EXAMPLES AND DESIGN

In the present investigation a numerical example consisting of a sandwich beam in three point bending will be considered. Due to symmetry, only half of the beam will be considered, see Fig 2, where the dimensions and the boundary conditions for the sandwich beam are given. The applied load is 15 N per mm thickness on the full panel, and the material properties for the sandwich constituents are given in Table 1. The geometry and the materials are the same as those considered by Bozhevolnaya et al. [4], who investigated sandwich structures consisting of aluminium face sheets and two types of PVC foam cores.

Fig. 2: Geometry and boundary conditions used for the numerical example.

Table 1: Material properties of sandwich beam constituents.

	Young's modulus	Shear modulus	Tensile strength
Faces (Aluminium)	$E = 70,000$ MPa		
Main core material (Divinycell H60)	$E = 60$ MPa*	$G = 22$ MPa	$\sigma_{ult} = 0.9$ MPa*
Core insert (Divinycell H250)	$E = 400$ MPa*	$G = 108$ MPa	$\sigma_{ult} = 5.8$ MPa*

*: compressive loading

Six different designs will be considered in the following. The first design assumes constant core stiffness over the entire sandwich beam length, see Fig. 3 (No reinforcement). This corresponds to the case where no reinforcement is introduced to carry the concentrated load. In the second design a stiffer core is introduced beneath the concentrated load, which is joined directly to the main core of the sandwich. This leads to a stiffness variation that corresponds to a step function, see Fig 3 (Butt junction).

Fig. 3: Stiffness variation through the length of the core for the different designs.

In the following designs a structurally graded ‘patch’ core is introduced between the main core and the core insert, as suggested by Bozhevolnaya et al. [9].

In the first two trial cases a structurally graded core material with a lengthwise linear stiffness variation is inserted between the core insert and the main core, thus ensuring a smooth variation of the core stiffness. Two different lengths of the structurally graded zone are evaluated: equal to the height of the sandwich beam (Linear 1x), and three times the sandwich beam thickness (Linear 3x), respectively.

The last two design cases feature structurally grading of the core stiffness corresponding to a cubic variation of the core stiffness, which is defined such that both the stiffness and the stiffness gradient is smooth through the length of the sandwich. Here the length of the structurally graded zone is also equal to either one time (Cubic 1x) or three times (Cubic 3x) the height of the sandwich beam, respectively. These two design cases are used to investigate the effect of smoothness of the core stiffness variations.

RESULTS

The high order sandwich beam theory has been applied for the analysis of the problem of three-point bending of a sandwich beam illustrated in Fig. 2.

The distribution of stresses in the top face is shown in Fig. 4 corresponding to the outer surface.

The design case ‘No reinforcement’ show an almost linear increase of stresses until the zone of load introduction is approached, where a dramatic increase of the stresses is found (Sandwich length = 180 mm).

Fig. 4: The in-plane normal stresses in the top face sheet at the upper boundary.

With the ‘Butt junction’ design the stress level in the face near the load is significantly lower near this point, but a new area of local increase of stresses is found near the junction between the main core and the core insert (Sandwich length = 130mm). (Note that the curve corresponding to ‘Butt junction’ coincide with the curves corresponding to ‘Linear 1x’, ‘Linear 3x’, ‘Cubic 1x’ and ‘Cubic 3x’ for ‘Sandwich length’ > 170 mm).

The design cases ‘Linear 1x’ and ‘Cubic 1x’ introduces a structurally graded core between the core insert and the mail core, and the effect is a decrease of the stresses in the faces near the core junction, although local stress concentrations are still present.

The design cases ‘Linear 3x’ and ‘Cubic 3x’, which introduce longer zones of structurally graded core, show an even lower local increase of the face stresses.

The shear stress in the core (τ_{xz}) is considered in Fig. 5. The design case ‘No reinforcement’ shows a constant shear stress in the core until the load introduction zone is approached. Here the load is transferred to the upper face sheet where the external load is applied.

The ‘Butt junction’ design case shows a large local variation of shear stress near the junction. The design cases ‘Linear 1x’ and ‘Cubic 1x’ display a significantly smaller disturbance of the local stresses at the core junction, and with the ‘Linear 3x’ and ‘Cubic 3x’ designs this disturbance has almost vanished.

Fig.5: The shear stress in the core. (Note that the shear stress is assumed to be constant through the thickness of the core according to the applied high-order sandwich theory).

The transverse normal stresses (σ_{zz}) in the core are considered in Fig. 6. For the ‘No reinforcement’ design case these stresses are zero except near the load introduction, where very high stresses are found. However, these stresses are even higher for the ‘Butt junction’ design. In addition, high stresses are found near the core junction with this design.

The structurally graded designs ‘Linear 1x’ and ‘Cubic 1x’ alleviate these stresses, and with the ‘Linear 3x’ and ‘Cubic 3x’ designs these stresses have almost vanished.

DISCUSSION

The results show that the design case with ‘No reinforcement’ is unable to carry substantial concentrated loading due to the high stress level in the faces and the transverse normal stresses in the core, considering that the strength of the main core material may be quite low (see Table 1).

With the ‘Butt junction’ design the stress level in the faces is reduced significantly, and although the transverse normal stresses in the core are increased, it should be remembered that the material used for the core insert is also stronger than the main core (see Table 1). There is, however, a new problem with this design, which is located at the interface between the main core and the core insert. The abrupt change of shear stiffness leads to new local bending effects, and subsequent increase of the stresses in the face sheets. In addition, the shear stresses and the transverse shear stresses are increased near the core junction.

Fig. 6: Transverse normal stress in core at the upper face core interface is shown. (Note that some curves coincide above ‘Sandwich length’ > 170 mm).

This analysis show a significant increase of the stresses at the junction, and a more detailed analysis of the butt junction problem performed on similar structures by Bozhevolnaya et al. [5] and by Bozhevolnaya and Lyckegaard [10] has shown that a singular stress state emerges near the three material junction of the two core materials and the face within the framework of linear theory of elasticity. The singular nature of the three materials junction has been investigated in detail by e.g. Pageau et. al. [11].

The results of the analyses of the two design cases ‘Linear 1x’ and ‘Cubic 1x’ show that the local bending of the face sheets is reduced, and that the stress peaks in the core materials are also reduced. The difference between these two design cases is, however, not significant. Thus, it appears that smoothness of the stiffness gradient is of secondary importance for the performance of the structurally graded core patch.

The analyses of the final design cases ‘Linear 3x’ and ‘Cubic 3x’ show that the local bending and the core stress peaks have almost disappeared. Hence, it seems that the optimal length of the structurally graded core patch is near this length. The difference between these two designs is again insignificant.

CONCLUSIONS

If concentrated loads are applied to sandwich structures, the stress level may increase significantly, which is shown by the analysis of sandwich structures with no reinforcements. The introduction of a core insert will improve this situation, i.e. the stress concentrations will

be reduced, but new difficulties arise in the vicinity of the junctions between core inserts and the main core due to the stiffness mismatch.

The performance of structurally graded core inserts has been compared with the case of uniform stiffness core inserts. The evaluation shows that the introduction of a structurally graded core insert may reduce the localised stresses induced in the vicinity of junctions between core inserts and main cores. If the structurally graded zone is long enough, then it is possible to almost remove the local increase of stresses.

Future developments include more detailed investigations of the performance of structurally graded core materials, which could also lead to a more detailed description of the properties of the optimal structural grading. If the entire core insert is subject to structural design, then it will be possible to introduce more localised reinforcements beneath the concentrated load, as well as anisotropic material properties if these properties are desirable.

In addition, future developments also includes methods and strategies for the design and manufacture of structurally graded sandwich core materials, as proposed theoretically in this paper. The concept has been demonstrated recently by Nygaard et. al. [12], who have developed, manufactured and tested structurally graded polymeric foam core materials

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